

SliceViz User Study

This questionnaire contains 5 sections. Please ensure you have the complete questionnaire before you start the study.

Section 1: Participant information

1. How much experience do you have with Java/Android development? (in years)

2. Rate your knowledge on the following on a scale of Beginner to Expert.

	Beginner	Novice	Intermediate	Advanced	Expert
Android app development	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Java development	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Understanding of Jimple	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Using static analysis tools	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Graph visualization	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Data privacy	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GDPR	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section 2: SliceViz Tasks

Task 1: Use the provided APK file to find privacy-related data sources using SliceViz. Then answer the following questions:

1.1. Which types of privacy-related data does this app collect? (Select all that apply)

- Risk 1 directly identifiable data
- Risk 2 partially identifiable data
- Risk 3 access data
- Risk 4 context-dependent data
- Personal data

1.2. Which of the collected data types require protection according to GDPR guidelines?

1.3. Which of the following privacy-related properties could you observe in the slices? (Select all that apply)

- Data minimization – app is collecting data which is not used. Data collection may not be necessary.
- Third-party API usage – app uses third-party API methods.
- No data protection – no technical measures such as encryption are used by the app.

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

1.4. The dashboard contains enough information to identify privacy-related features

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Explain

Task 2: Use the provided APK file to examine the Java and Jimple view of the program slice(s).

2.1. In general, program slice was easier to understand with:

- Java View
- Jimple View

Explain.

2.2. In general, program slice was faster to understand with:

- Java View
- Jimple View

Explain.

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

2.3. I am comfortable with Java view.

2.4. What are the positive points of Java view?

2.5. What are the negative points of Java view?

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

2.6. I am comfortable with Jimple view.

2.12. How likely is it you would recommend Jimple view over Java view to a friend?

<input type="checkbox"/>										
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
(Not at all)										(Go for it!)

Explain.

Task 3: Visualize the given program slice. Then answer the following questions:

3.1. Which types of privacy-related data does this program slice collect? (Select all that apply)

- Risk 1 directly identifiable data
- Risk 2 partially identifiable data
- Risk 3 access data
- Risk 4 context-dependent data
- Personal data

3.2. Which of the following privacy-related properties could you observe in the slice? (Select all that apply)

- Data minimization – program slices is collecting data which is not used. Data collection may not be necessary.
- Third-party API usage – program slice uses third-party API methods.
- No data protection – no technical measures such as encryption are used by the program slice.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
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3.3. I could understand the slice easily without access to the dashboard.

<input type="checkbox"/>				
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3.4. I would prefer to have an overview and the hints provided by the dashboard.

<input type="checkbox"/>				
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Section 3: Usability

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
1. I would like to use SliceViz for my privacy-aware development needs.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2. I found SliceViz unnecessarily complex.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3. I found SliceViz easy to use.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4. I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use SliceViz.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5. I found the various functions in SliceViz to be well integrated.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in SliceViz.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use SliceViz very quickly.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8. I found SliceViz very cumbersome to use.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
9. I felt confident using SliceViz.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with SliceViz.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section 4: Net Promoter Score

1. How likely is it you would recommend SliceViz to an Android developer?

<input type="checkbox"/>										
0 (Not at all)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10 (Go for it!)

Explain.

Section 5: Open questions

1. What features would you like in SliceViz?

2. What are the positive points of SliceViz?

3. What are the negative points of SliceViz?

4. Was the given documentation useful?

5. Did SliceViz give you a better understanding of privacy-relevant data processing?

If yes, please specify which parts of SliceViz were most helpful in identifying privacy-relevant information.

If no, please share any suggestions for improvement or explain what you found unclear.

6. Other remarks.